

NUMERICAL SIMULATION OF CFRP TRANSVERSE FAILURE CONSIDERING NON-LINEAR VISCOELASTIC/PLASTIC CONSTITUTIVE EQUATION WITH ENTROPY DAMAGE

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ABSTRACT

A viscoelastic/plastic model of resin based on irreversible thermodynamics and viscoelastic theory is suggested in order to predict the failure of CFRP matrix resin. Single axis tensile tests and creep-recovery tests are performed under various temperature and strain rates to identify the material properties. The change of viscoelastic properties with temperature and strain rate are converted using the time-temperature superposition principle. The proposed model can express the strain behavior of creep and recovery process. In numerical analysis, A FORTRAN program is created to introduce a proposed nonlinear viscoelastic model into matrix resin. Failure analysis of unidirectional CFRP is performed under various temperatures and strain rates. The analysis model can express the progress damage of CFRP.

1 INTRODUCTION

Heat-resistant carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) composed of TriA-X polyimide resin have been developed for application to titanium materials, such as the inner frame structure of turbofan engines. Therefore, its long-term durability under high temperature environment is required. In this study, an objective is the durability relate to the transverse tensile failure of unidirectional heat-resistant CFRP. The transverse failure is initial damage for CFRP laminates [1], it triggers delamination. The matrix resin plays a large role in the development of CFRP having high strength and excellent heat resistance. Furthermore, considering that the base materials of general composite materials are polymer materials, its characteristics depend on time and temperature. The time dependent properties of polymeric materials are explained using the theories such as viscoelasticity and viscoplasticity. In this study, we propose a new non-linear viscoelastic/plastic model of resin based on irreversible thermodynamics and viscoelastic theory, and aim to predict failure of CFRP matrix resin. In the damage law, we introduce a thermodynamic entropy to material damage. It has been attempted to clarify the damage evolution in solid materials from irreversible thermodynamics in recent years [2]. The entropy damage is defined by dissipation energy of stress-strain relationship in this study. The tensile test and creep recovery test are conducted to calculate entropy damage and to determine the viscoelastic parameters, respectively. The failure prediction of tensile test under various strain rate are calculated by using the new non-linear viscoelastic/plastic constitutive law considering entropy damage.

2 MODELING OF MATRIX RESIN

2.1 Non-linear viscoelastic/plastic constitutive equation

In this study, we use the model as shown Fig.1.

Fig. 1 Viscoelastic/plastic model.

The all strain ε is constituted by non-linear viscoelastic strain ε_{ve} (from Maxwell model) and permanent strain ε_{vp} (Eq. (1)). Eq. (2) express the proposed non-linear viscoelastic/plastic constitutive law considering entropy damage. J is creep compliance as shown Eq. (3), D is damage variable based on thermodynamic entropy, Σ_n is stress considering non-linearity (Eq. (4)) and n_{vp} is a viscosity coefficient. In Eq. (3), J_0 is a initial creep compliance equal to inverse of a Young's modulus ($1/E_0$), t is the time, τ_c is a relaxation time and n is power law. In Eq. (4), σ is applied stress, σ_0 is the certain stress and m is non-linearity exponent. These the permanent strain parameters and viscoelastic parameters are determined from fitting results of the creep and recovery test, and the tensile tests. The detail of damage variable based on thermodynamic entropy D is described later.

$$\varepsilon = \varepsilon_{ve} + \varepsilon_{vp} \quad (1)$$

$$\varepsilon(t) = \int_{-\infty}^t \frac{J(t-t')}{(1-D)} \frac{\left(\frac{dD}{1-D} \Sigma_n + d\Sigma_n \right)}{dt'} dt' + \int_0^t \frac{\Sigma_n}{\eta_{vp}} dt. \quad (2)$$

$$J(t) = J_0 \left(1 + \left(\frac{t}{\tau_c} \right)^n \right) \quad (3)$$

$$\Sigma_n(\sigma) = \sigma \left(1 + \left(\frac{\langle \sigma - \sigma_0 \rangle}{\sigma_0} \right)^m \right) \quad (4)$$

2.2 Time-temperature superposition principle

Linear viscoelastic behavior of polymers obeys the time-temperature superposition principle [3], as has been known for more than thirty years. This principle states that viscoelastic characteristic functions measured at different temperatures may be brought to coincide by parallel shifts along the logarithmic time or frequency axis. If, for instance, $E(t, T)$ represents elastic modulus as a function of time t at the temperature T , functions at temperatures T and T_R should be connected by the relation:

$$E(t, T) = E(a \times t, T_R) \quad (5)$$

$$a = a(T, T_R) = \frac{t}{t'} \quad (6)$$

and is a function of the temperatures T and T_R only. $\log a(T, T_R)$ is the shift to be applied along the logarithmic time axis to obtain superposition. It is called the time-temperature shift function. Time-

temperature superposition principle has various type. In this study Arrhenius type [4] is used and shift factor is expressed quantitatively as

$$\log a_{T_R} = \frac{\Delta H}{2.303R} \left(\frac{1}{T} - \frac{1}{T_R} \right) \quad (7)$$

where ΔH is activation energy. According to previous research, the activation energy of TriA-X polyimide resin is determined to be 160 kJ/mol. This value is used in this research.

2.3 Failure criteria of matrix resin

It has been attempted to clarify the damage evolution in solid materials from irreversible thermodynamics in recent years [5-8]. Permanent deterioration is a manifestation of an irreversible process according to the second law of thermodynamics. That is, deterioration of the material proceeds with the disorder of the system. And disorder in the system, which causes deterioration of the characteristics, is raised by the deformation of materials, and the entropy increases accordingly. The disorder in the degraded system continues to increase to the critical state and causes the failure of the materials [9,10]. Therefore, irreversible entropy in materials is expected to be a criterion for evaluating durability of materials. Amount entropy generation until material failure γ_f (fracture entropy) is described as shown Eq. (8) by the first law of thermodynamics, the second of thermodynamics and the Helmholtz's free energy per unit mass.

$$\gamma_f = \int_0^{t_f} \left(\frac{W_p}{T} - \frac{\mathbf{A}_k : \dot{\mathbf{V}}_k}{T} - J_q \frac{\text{grad}T}{T^2} \right) dt \quad (8)$$

Where W_p is plastic strain energy, \mathbf{A}_k is a generalization force associated with the internal variable \mathbf{V}_k , J_q is the heat flux and T is temperature. The first term in Eq. (8) is mechanical dissipation due to plastic deformation, the second term is dissipation due to unrecoverable energy accumulated in the material due to damage and strain hardening, and the third term is thermal dissipation owing to heat conduction, respectively. In the process accompanying large deformation, entropy generation by plastic deformation is dominant, so entropy generation by heat conduction in the third term is negligible [9]. Thus, we assume Eq. (9) as the dissipation energy. The equation shows that it is possible to calculate fracture entropy by measuring dissipation energy and temperature during the experimental test. Eq. (10) shows the damage valuable introducing the fracture entropy. D_{cr} is the critical damage, α is material coefficient for damage. These parameters are defined from load-unload testing results.

$$\gamma_f = \int_0^{t_f} \left(\frac{W_p}{T} - \frac{\mathbf{A}_k : \dot{\mathbf{V}}_k}{T} \right) dt = \int_0^{t_f} \frac{W}{T} dt \quad (9)$$

$$D = D_{cr}(1 - e^{-\alpha\gamma_f}) \quad (10)$$

3 IDENTIFICATION OF MATERIAL PARAMETERS

3.1 Creep and recovery test

The permanent strain characteristics and viscoelastic characteristics are calculated from these tests. The creep recovery test is conducted under room temperature (300 K) and 373 K environment. In the test, the specimen is subjected to a load at a constant speed (35 N/s) up to the different holding stress in each test. After that load the stress for 1 hour, then remove the stress at the same speed as during loading. The holding stress in tests at room temperature are 20, 40, 60, 80 MPa in each test. The experimental result and prediction of strain behavior in the creep and recovery test is shown in Fig. 2. Here, the entropy damage which is obtained from tensile test is considered. The new non-linear viscoelastic/plastic can express the behavior of viscoelastic materials because of the good agreement between experimental

results and predictions. Parameters of viscoelastic model obtained from the fittings are shown in table 1.

Fig. 2 Strain behavior prediction of all creep and recovery tests

Table 1 Material parameters used in viscoelastic model

Material parameters				
Continuous Maxwell's parameters				
i	E_i	η_i	Nonlinear	
1	265	1.0E+04	σ_0 [MPa]	120
2	265	7.5E+05	m	1.3
3	265	7.5E+06		
4	265	5.0E+08	Permanent strain	
5	265	2.5E+09	σ_y [MPa]	21
6	265	5.0E+09	η_{vp} [MPa·s]	6.21×10^7
7	265	5.0E+10	p	1
8	265	5.0E+12		
9	265	1.0E+13	Damage parameters	
10	265	2.5E+14	D_{cr}	1.0
11	265	3.0E+15	α [$\mu\text{m}^3\text{K}/\text{J}$]	27
12	265	2.5E+16	γ_f [kJ/Km ³]	17.5
13	265	1.0E+18		
14	265	2.0E+20		
15	265	1.0E+23		

4 FAILURE SIMULATION OF CFRP

4.1 Analysis model

The unit cell model of CFRP used for analysis is shown in Fig. 3. In this study, FORTRAN programming language is used for introducing the suggested model into the analysis software ABAQUS (Dassault Systèmes). The element constructs the model is a two-dimensional quadrilateral element, and the analysis condition is a plane stress state. The cell size was $39\ \mu\text{m}$ in both longitudinal and lateral directions, and 30 fibers with a diameter of $6\ \mu\text{m}$ were inserted into the cell. The part surrounded by the circle in Fig. 3 is a fiber, and the other part is a matrix resin. The fibers were assumed to be fully elastic and the material properties of Table 1 were entered. In this analysis, the Poisson's ratio of the matrix ν_m and the fiber ν_f were both 0.3. In addition, material properties of TriA-X polyimide determined in "IDENTIFICATION OF MATERIAL PARAMETERS" were introduced into the matrix resin.

Table 1 Elastic modulus of fiber and Poisson's ratio

E_f [MPa]	14000
ν_f	0.3
ν_m	0.3

Fig. 3 2D unit cell model

4.2 Analysis results and discussion

The progress of damage during analysis is shown in Fig. 4. The shade of color in the figure shows the magnitude of the entropy value. In the red part, the entropy generation amount is large and the damage value is also large. It is observed that damage value is large in the place where the distance between the fibers is small, and the stress concentration is large in such place, thus it is easy to progress the damage.

Fig. 4 The evolution of damage in tensile process

5 CONCLUSIONS

The proposed material model is a nonlinear viscoelastic/plastic model including viscoelastic behavior depending on time, damage based on irreversible thermodynamics and permanent strain. Single axis tensile tests and creep-recovery tests are performed under various temperature and strain rates to identify the material properties. The proposed model can predict the strain behavior at creep and recovery condition. Numerical simulation of matrix failure is conducted under simple tension of radial direction of unidirectional CFRP using the introduced model. Numerical analysis model can express the progress damage of CFRP.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Hosoi, H. Kawada “Fatigue Life Prediction for Transverse Crack Initiation of CFRP Cross-Ply and Quasi-Isotropic Laminates”. *Materials*, Vo. 11, No. 7, in-press, 2018.
- [2] M. Naderi and M. M. Khonsari “An experimental approach to low-cycle fatigue damage based on thermodynamic entropy”. *International journal of solids and structures*, Vo. 47, No. 6, 2010, pp. 875-880.
- [3] J. Koyanagi, Y. Sato, T. Sasayama, et al. “Numerical simulation of strain-rate dependent transition of transverse tensile failure mode in fiber-reinforced composites.” *Composites Part A*, Vo. 56, 2014, pp. 136–142.
- [4] J. Koyanagi, S. Yoneyama, A. Nemoto, et al. “Time and temperature dependence of carbon/epoxy interface strength.” *Compos. Sci. Technol.* Vo. 70, 2010, pp. 1395–1400.
- [5] K. Dusan. “Damage mechanics: accomplishments, trends and needs.” *International Journal of Solids and Structures* Vo.37, 2000, pp. 267-277.
- [6] T. Hong and C. Basaran. “A damage mechanics-based fatigue life prediction model for solder joints.” *Journal of Electronic Packaging* Vo. 125, No.1, 2003, pp. 120-125.
- [7] F. M. A. Pires, et al. “Numerical modelling of ductile plastic damage in bulk metal forming.” *International journal of mechanical sciences* Vo. 45, No. 2, 2003, pp. 273-294.
- [8] L.S. Langer, E. Bouchbinder, and T Lookman. “Thermodynamic theory of dislocation-mediated plasticity.” *Acta Materialia* Vo. 58, No. 10, 2010, pp. 3718-3732.
- [9] M. Naderi, M. Amiri and M. M. Khonsari. “On the thermodynamic entropy of fatigue fracture.” *Proceedings of the Royal Society A: Mathematical, Physical and Engineering Sciences* Vo. 466, 2009, pp. 423-438.
- [10] C. Basaran, and N. Shihua. “An irreversible thermodynamics theory for damage mechanics of solids.” *International Journal of Damage Mechanics* Vo. 13, No. 3, 2004, pp. 205-223.